

Review

A meta-analysis on the impact of trees on yield of intercrops in alley-cropping systems of temperate climates

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Meta-analysis on the grain yield of arable intercrops in temperate alley-cropping.
- 30 % average yield reduction in alley-cropping compared to full sun from 18 trials.
- The negative effect of trees on yield increases with tree vicinity and tree aging.
- Trees have lower detrimental impact on winter, especially barley, vs. summer crops.
- Less detrimental or positive impact under low rainfall and high evapotranspiration.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

CONTEXT: The environmental benefits of agroforestry have been highlighted worldwide, although improved intercrop productivity has been clearly demonstrated only in the tropics.

OBJECTIVE AND METHODS: This meta-analysis aimed at summarizing knowledge from 18 trials on grain yield of arable intercrops in alley-cropping systems of temperate climates, within a mixed-effect model framework.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS: A general negative impact of trees on crop grain yield was documented, with an average reduction by 30 % compared to full sun, across the whole inter-row of wheat, barley, soybean and maize. Key findings included: (i) distance from trees is the major driver of the grain yield response, with increasing impact in the vicinity of the tree row, (ii) significance of crop phenology and species choice, with lower impact on winter vs. summer crops; (iii) tree age is the only relevant variable of the woody component, with increasing impact with aging; and (iv) available rainfall and potential evapotranspiration are key moderators, with a less detrimental or positive impact of trees under low rainfall and high evapotranspiration. This study also describes the implications of some tree design and management practices: (i) branchless tree rows allows for halving the alley width where crop yield is negatively affected by the tree line compared to a hedgerow, (ii) crop yield

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recovers at distances (D) from the tree row at which D/tree height approaches 1, this suggesting the interrow should be at least twice the maximum height of trees, (iii) intercrop should be varied across the tree cycle, by cultivating high shade-tolerant species/varieties when the tree age is >8 years.

SIGNIFICANCE: This meta-analysis underscores the need for further empirical studies on other intercrops and within climatic zones where limited data is currently available.

1. Introduction

The role of silvoarable practices in mitigating the impact of climate change on farming systems, while providing a considerable variety of ecosystem services, has been largely documented both in tropical and temperate environments. Numerous review studies and meta-analyses, particularly from tropics and subtropics, have summarized the benefits of integrating trees with crops, with a focus on carbon sequestration (Kumara et al., 2023; Cerda et al., 2019; Santos et al., 2019) and soil-mediated ecosystem services (Muchane et al., 2020; Kuyah et al., 2019). At global scale, the transition from conventional agriculture to agroforestry might significantly increase soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks by 26 %, 40 %, and 34 % in the 0–15, 0–30, and 0–100 cm depth interval respectively (De Stefano and Jacobson, 2018), with averagely 126 t ha⁻¹ additional carbon within 1 m depth soil layer (Shi et al., 2018) and 46.1 t ha⁻¹ within the tree biomass compared with sole cropland- or pasture-based land uses (Ma et al., 2020). In tropical areas, SOC can peak within five years, reaching equilibrium rapidly (Ma et al., 2020), whereas in temperate regions, SOC increases at a slower rate, requiring approximately a decade to observe measurable benefits and likely 35 years to reach equilibrium (Pardon et al., 2017; Ivezić et al., 2022; Mayer et al., 2022).

While capturing CO₂ from the atmosphere into stable carbon pools, agroforestry tree systems provide numerous ecosystem services at both below and aboveground level that sustain stable crop production. In humid and sub-humid tropics, agroforestry can reduce soil erosion by up to 50 % and improve water balance compared to monoculture (Muchane et al., 2020). Higher soil moisture content in tropical agroforestry systems is linked to improved soil infiltration rates and reduced evapotranspiration, facilitated by better soil hydraulic conductivity, soil porosity, and microclimate modifications associated to windbreak effect (Nyamadzawo et al., 2008; Kuyah et al., 2019; Siriri et al., 2013). Improvements in the nutrients cycle have also been extensively documented in the tropics, as a result of higher overall above and belowground C input by pruning residues, litterfall, root exudates and turnover, leading to 46 % and 11 % increases of N and available P, respectively, under agroforestry compared to monoculture (Muchane et al., 2020).

In temperate climates, similar patterns have been highlighted by various empirical studies, followed by some attempts to summarize the key findings across the whole temperate zone (Dmuchowski et al., 2024; Sollen-Norrlin et al., 2020) or Europe (Torralba et al., 2016). The major findings indicate that trees in agroforestry can mitigate microclimate extremes, reducing evapotranspiration, soil erosion, while improving soil nutrients availability (Cardinael et al., 2021; Dmuchowski et al., 2024) and enhancing biodiversity (Torralba et al., 2016; Edo et al., 2024).

Despite extensive recognition of agroforestry's environmental benefits, evidence for enhanced intercrop productivity is mostly limited to tropical climates, where under-canopy crops like coffee and cacao perform well in shaded conditions (Nesper et al., 2017; Mokondoko et al., 2022; Mattalia et al., 2022), and in poor soils and arid climates (Bayala and Prieto, 2020; Kuyah et al., 2019; Durand-Bessart et al., 2020). In temperate zones, crop yield response is variable, due to interspecific competition for natural resources, land use, and diverse pedo-climatic conditions. Evidence suggests that silvoarable systems often outperform monocultures regarding land use efficiency, as supported by favorable land equivalent ratios (LER) (Mead and Willey,

1980) ranging from 0.95 to 2, depending on pedo-climatic zones and agricultural management (Sereke et al., 2015; García de Jalón et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2019; Lehmann et al., 2020; Pent, 2020). While early research focused primarily on environmental benefits, recent studies have demonstrated that higher LERs in silvoarable systems result from improved use efficiency of both agricultural land and natural resources, such as solar radiation and water. These resources limited availability concerns an increasing number of farmers in temperate climates (Graves et al., 2007; Wolz and DeLucia, 2018). Although farmers recognize these benefits, they often perceive silvoarable practices as economically unviable, as revealed by several surveys assessing farmers' opinions on barriers to the integration of trees into agricultural land (Smith et al., 2012; Trozzo et al., 2014; Rois-Díaz et al., 2018; Sereke et al., 2015). This is among the main obstacles to a broader adoption of silvoarable practices across temperate climate zones (Eichhorn et al., 2006; García de Jalón et al., 2018; Bettles et al., 2021; Tavernier et al., 2024; Tranchina et al., 2024), depending on scattered and contrasting information on yield of intercrops available in the literature. Indeed, across various crop and tree species, design characteristics, management choices and pedo-climatic conditions, crop yield in silvoarable systems was either reduced (Burgess et al., 2005; Tsonkova et al., 2012; Swieter et al., 2019; Inurreta-Aguirre et al., 2018; Pardon et al., 2018) or enhanced (Moreno, 2008; Piotto et al., 2024; Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2021) as compared to full sun conditions without trees.

Comprehensive information on agroforestry systems of the temperate climates derived from case studies that are summarized by meta-analyses, as attempts to provide synthetic key drivers of crop yield response. Van Vooren et al. (2017), by focusing on silvoarable systems with hedgerows (HR) highlighted a significant effect of the distance from trees on crop yield, with reduced productivity close to the HR and gradually restoring when the distance-to- tree height ratio (D/H) increases. Over 60 studies from temperate climates, these authors have demonstrated a negative impact on crop yield within a D/H 0–2.1 interval, estimating a relative crop yield within this area of 79 %, although neither crop choice nor HR characteristics (e.g., species, age, orientation) were found significant explanatory variables. The adverse effect of reduced distance from trees on relative crop yield was also confirmed by Ivezić et al. (2021), who investigated modern alley cropping systems and traditional systems with scattered trees such as Dehesas, making comparisons between Northern and Southern Europe. Over 13 European studies, these researchers documented that the relative crop yield tend to be higher in Dehesa than in alley cropping, while the latter provided similar impact in northern and southern Europe, and relative yield of fodder tend to be lower than those of cereals in alley cropping (Ivezić et al., 2021). More recently, Scordia et al. (2023) investigated the impact of the tree species, tree cover, crop species, and agronomic management on crop productivity, with a focus on agroforestry systems from semi-arid to warm temperate Mediterranean areas. In such a study, the distance from trees was not investigated, but crop and tree species choice, and soil coverage by trees resulted as significant explanatory variables, across 21 Mediterranean studies (Scordia et al., 2023).

Within this framework, a comprehensive summary of crop yield responses in temperate alley-cropping systems is still lacking. There currently is an urgent need to summarize results from a wide range of pedo-climatic conditions in the temperate area, for identifying the best system designs, tree management and tree-crop combinations for maximizing crop productivity in alley silvoarable systems. This study aims to integrate existing knowledge on crop yield in silvoarable alley

cropping systems from diverse temperate regions, with a focus on arable grain crops and alley-cropping systems. Grain crops play a major role in the diet of a vast part of the global population, but increasingly affected by climate extremes (Challinor et al., 2014; Rezaei et al., 2023). Alley-cropping is the most promising design for the implementation of high-productive silvoarable systems in temperate regions, as a result of the facilitation of mechanical operation as compared to scattered designs. Specifically, addressed research questions (RQ) and hypotheses (H) were as follows:

RQ.1. Does the impact of trees on the grain yield of intercrops vary according to the distance from the tree row? H.1. The most relevant yield reductions are expected close to the tree line.

RQ.2. Does the impact of trees vary according to crop phenology and species? H.2. Summer crops are expected to be more negatively affected by trees as compared to winter crops.

RQ.3. Are there specific tree characteristics and system design that attenuate the impact on grain yield of intercrops? H.3. Tree age and row orientation are expected to be relevant moderators.

RQ.4. Does the impact of trees vary according to climatic variables? H.4. Yield reduction of intercrops in the vicinity of the tree row is expected to be attenuated under high temperature and low rainfall.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Literature search

A systematic literature search was conducted using Scopus and Web of Science, for peer-reviewed studies focused on grain crop yield response in silvoarable agroforestry systems (AF) compared to adjacent controls under full sun without trees (C). This search covered studies from January 1980 to December 2022 (see detailed search string in SI.1). Silvoarable agroforestry is defined as intercropping with widely spaced tree rows (Dupraz and Newman, 1997), where trees can be distributed following various designs, such as alley cropping, isolated/scattered trees or line belts (Mosquera-Losada et al., 2009). The main purpose here was to summarize the effect of row-arranged trees on the yield of the neighboring arable crops, thereby the definition of silvoarable was restricted to alley cropping and line belts, excluding studies with isolated/scattered trees. Case studies on hedgerow were included only when trees were pruned regularly and shrubs were absent under the trees; the other cases of hedgerow, as well as pollarded trees were excluded from the analysis.

The systematic literature search was performed accordingly to the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009) and the process is described in SI.2. After the removal of duplicates, the literature search yielded 1109 references. A primary screening of the candidate studies for further analysis was carried out based on title and abstract, with the following criteria: (i) study site is located within temperate regions defined by Köppen-Geiger climate classification, regardless Northern and Southern hemisphere (Beck et al., 2018; SI.3), (ii) empirical data on intercrop grain yield are available, but reviews and modelling studies were excluded, (iii) studies are located in natural open field with real tree rows: pot and greenhouse studies, as well as artificial shading trials were excluded, (iv) true controls are present nearby the silvoarable field/plot, allowing yield comparison with and without tree rows. With the use of these criteria, 15 studies were retained. Additionally, to retrieve as many relevant studies as possible, a further search through the reference lists of these papers was carried out. In total, 18 original research studies that met the inclusion criteria were selected for further analysis of their data collection (see SI.4, SI.5). Of these, 10 studies were from Europe, 1 from North America, 3 from South America, 1 from Africa and 3 from Asia (SI.6) (Fig. 1).

2.2. Data extraction from selected primary studies

For each selected study, the mean, sample size (when available) and relative estimates of uncertainty such as standard error or standard deviation of intercrop grain yield under the presence of the tree row (AF) and without (C), were extracted. Data were retrieved directly from tables or the main text, and the software WebPlotDigitizer (Rohatgi, 2015) was used to retrieve data available from graphs only. When available, data across different sites (i.e., coordinate locations), and years within the same study were extracted.

Following the first hypothesis (H.1) regarding yield variation across the inter-row, for each site and year, all the available data of crop yield at different distances and both sides from the tree rows were extracted. Each observation (equal to one row in the dataset) represented a comparison between the grain yield of a specific crop in AF at a defined distance and side from the tree row, and the yield of the same crop in an adjacent control setting without trees (C). When only an average yield for the entire area between two adjacent tree rows was reported, the midpoint of the inter-row was used as the distance reference, with the following number of observations for each crop: 102 for wheat, 33 for barley, 5 for triticale, 26 for soybean, and 51 for maize (SI.6). Since the

Fig. 1. Geographical distribution of the 18 original studies identified through systematic literature search. For each study, point size depict the number of observations available and the colors the temperate climate subgroups, i.e., mediterranean (MC; including both warm and hot summers – mediterranean climates subgroups), oceanic (OC), and warm temperature with hot summer (WT).

number of observations for triticale was excessively low to allow any robust analysis, this crop was excluded from the study. Wheat and barley, being always cultivated during winter-spring months, were also referred to as winter crops, while soybean and maize as summer crops.

Additionally, a set of moderator variables was collected to potentially explain heterogeneity in effect sizes. These moderators included (i) study site characteristics (latitude, longitude, altitude, country, and city), (ii) climatic variables, (iii) crop and tree attributes, and (iv) agroforestry design parameters. Since the climatic variables were often absent or reported for incomplete measurement period, they were retrieved from the Comprehensive Environmental Data Archive (CEDA), using the Climatic Research Unit (CRU) Time-Series (TS) version 4.04 of high-resolution (0.5 × 0.5 degree) gridded data of month-by-month variation in climate (Jan. 1901- Dec. 2019) (Harris et al., 2020). TS are produced by CRU at the University of East Anglia funded by the UK National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS), as a NERC collaborative Centre. Given the coordinates of each study site, the monthly average air temperature (temp; degree Celsius) and potential evapotranspiration (pet; mm), and the monthly rainfall (rain; mm) were extracted from CEDA archive. The aridity index (arid) was calculated as the ratio between rain and pet (Zomer et al., 2008).

For each study site and year the above four climatic variables were expressed either as growing season means (tempG, rainG, petG, aridG) and as yearly mean (tempY, rainY, petY, aridY). The G variables were calculated by averaging the monthly climatic data between sowing and harvesting. For winter crops, which grow across two subsequent calendar years, the Y variables considered the year of the vegetative and reproductive growth, i.e., the second calendar year only. Each study site was classified also by the temperate climate subgroup of belonging, according to the Köppen-Geiger classification (Beck et al., 2018). Accordingly, three climate subgroups were identified: mediterranean (MC; including both the warm and the hot summers – mediterranean climates subgroups), oceanic (OC), and warm temperature with hot

summer (WT). Lastly, each study site was defined by the categorical ‘contrast_zone_TR4’ variable, that was created to categorize rainfall and temperature combinations at each site, as described in Table 1, and further detailed in SI.7 and SI.8.

Crop-specific data included crop species, sowing and harvesting times, and side and distance from the tree row; the cultivar name was also extracted as potential moderator, although available only in about half of the observations. Regarding tree characteristics, the following moderators were collected, when available: tree species, cultivar/clone, age, height, diameter at breast height (DBH) and canopy width. Design characteristics of the agroforestry systems, that were collected from primary studies, were: tree row orientation, inter-row distance, intra-row distance and population density.

When only part of the above information was reported in a study, the authors were contacted to gaining the missing information.

Different formats of potential explanatory variables were tested, either numerical or categorical, as described in Table 1, and further detailed in SI.7.

2.3. Effect size calculation

The log response ratio (RR) was calculated as a measure of the effect size (Hedges et al., 1999):

$$RR = \ln\left(\frac{Response_{AF}}{Response_C}\right)$$

For each observation, the response ratio was calculated between the mean response, i.e., crop grain yield at harvest in agroforestry (Response_{AF}) at a specific distance from the tree row, and the mean response of that crop in the adjacent open field control (Response_C) without trees. In this way, a positive response ratio (RR > 0) means that the presence of the tree row has a positive effect on crop yield, while a negative value (RR < 0) a negative effect, and close to zero (RR ≈ 0)

Table 1

List of explanatory variables tested along model screening, both in numerical (N) and categorical (C) formats, with reference to the model group (for more details see: Table 2, SI.7, SI.8 and SI.12). For climate variables: G = data for growing season, Y = yearly data.

Model group	Variable extended	Variable code	Variable format	Description	
BASE	Distance from tree-row	ln_DH	N	ln(D/H)	
		D/H	C	D/H ≤ 0.25; D/H > 0.25 & ≤ 0.50; D/H > 0.50 & ≤ 1.00; D/H > 1.00	
CORE	Crop phenology	crop_pheno	C	winter crops (barley, common wheat); summer crops (soybean, maize)	
	Crop species	crop_species	C	barley; wheat; maize; soybean	
		tree_age_orig	N	original variable	
AGE	Tree age	tree_age_log2	N	log2(original variable)	
		tree_age_C2	C	young (≤8 years old); old (>9 years old)	
		tree_age_C3	C	young (≤8 years old); middle (≤9 & > 16 years old); old (>17 years old)	
		tree_height	N	original variable	
TREEROW	Tree species	tree_species	C	13 species (for a complete list, see Table SI.7)	
	Tree growth cycle	tree_growth_C2	C	Fast versus slow growing (for a complete list, see Table SI.7)	
	Intra-row distance	tree_dinrow_C3	C	low (≤4 m); intermediate (≤4 & > 7 m); high (> 7 m)	
	Tree-row orientation	tree_orient_C3	C	N-S (North-South); E-W (East-West), NW-SE (North West – South East)	
	Side of the tree-row	tree_side_C3	C	E (East); W (West); Others (North, South, Centre of the alley)	
	Temperate climate subgroup (Köppen-Geiger categories)	clim_zone_KG	C	MC (warm summer and hot summer mediterranean climates); OC (oceanic climate); WT (warm temperature with hot summer climate)	
	Contrasting climatic conditions	clim_zone_TR4		C	high °C & high mm (14–26 °C & 500–900 mm); low °C & high mm (7–14 °C & 500–900 mm); high °C & low mm (14–26 °C & 100–500 mm); low °C and low mm (7–14 °C & 100–500 mm)
				C	
CLIMATE	Air temperature (X = G/Y)	tempX_orig	N	original variable	
		tempX_log2	N	log2 (original variable)	
		tempX_pred	C	low, middle, high (for the class boundaries, see SI.8)	
	Rainfall (X = G/Y)	rainX_orig	N	original variable	
		rainX_log2	N	log2 (original variable)	
		rainX_pred	C	low, middle, high (for the class boundaries, see SI.8)	
	Potential evapotranspiration (X = G/Y)	petX_orig	N	original variable	
		petX_log2	N	log2 (original variable)	
		petX_pred	C	low, middle, high (for the class boundaries, see SI.8)	
		aridX_orig	N	original variable	
Aridity index (X = G/Y)	aridX_log2	N	log2 (original variable)		
	aridX_pred	C	low, middle, high (for the class boundaries, see SI.8)		

little or no effect. Since most of the studies provided yield data for multiple distances from the tree rows, RR was calculated for each distance relative to the control fields.

Since this calculation violates independence assumptions of the effect sizes (Olkin and Gleser, 2009; i.e., multiple Response_{AF} values compared to one Response_C), this was accounted for the correlation among effect sizes by computing the variance–covariance (VCV) matrix proposed by Lajeunesse (2011), using the ‘v.calc’ function of the R package *metafor*. The VCV matrix models the dependencies that arise when using the same control group and estimating multiple effect sizes (Lajeunesse, 2016). The inverse of the square root of the sampling variance of the VCV matrix was used to weight the precision of the effect size (Lajeunesse, 2011). To compute the VCV matrix, the sampling variance of each pairwise comparison was calculated based on Hedges et al. (1999), as ~follows:

$$\sigma(RR) = \left(\frac{SD_C}{N_C Response_C} \right) + \left(\frac{SD_{AF}}{N_{AF} Response_{AF}} \right)$$

where SD is the standard deviation of the mean and N denotes the number of replicates (plots) for AF and C settings. As the estimate of uncertainty of grain yield was not always available in the studies, when this information was not obtained by the authors, missing SD values were imputed using the coefficient of variation from all complete cases using the ‘impute.SD’ function of the R package *metagear* (Lajeunesse, 2016). In this way, it was possible to apply a conventional meta-analysis with weighting of the different observations by their variances on the full dataset (Gurevitch et al., 2018).

To test the overall effect of agroforestry on grain yield, the summary effect size was calculated, as well as the total heterogeneity (τ^2) across different studies, considering 95 % credible (i.e., Bayesian confidence) intervals (CI). The existence of publication bias was assessed using funnel plots (Peters et al., 2008), and specifically the ‘funnel’ function of the R package *metafor* (Viechtbauer, 2010); the Egger’s test modification proposed by Nakagawa and Santos (2012) were applied to assess funnel plots’ asymmetry of the null models’ residuals.

2.4. A mixed-effect regression approach

A mixed-effect regression model framework was set up to investigate and quantify the four research hypotheses (RQ1 – RQ4). Regression modelling was possible as the full datasets of the studies were available with yield expressed along with its distance to the tree row and many other background characteristics. The overarching format of the models was as follows:

Table 2
Details of the steps of the forward regression, in accordance with the research questions.

Model step	Research question	Type of moderators	Competing models List of moderators	Output model
Step 1	RQ1	Crop distance from the tree row	Null model Crop distance	Base
Step 2	RQ2	Crop type Crop phenology	Base model & Crop phenology Base model & Crop species	Core
Step 3	RQ3	Tree row characteristics	Core model & Tree age Core model & Tree height Core model & Tree species Core model & Tree growth cycle Core model & Tree row orientation Core model & Intra-row distance Core model & Side of the tree row	Many competing models
Step 4	RQ4	Climatic characteristics	Core model & Climatic zone Core model & Temperature Core model & Rainfall Core model & Potential evapotranspiration Core model & Aridity index	

$$RR \sim f_1(Distance) * (f_2(Crop) + f_3(Tree_{row}) + f_4(Climate)) + (1|Study:Site)$$

The fixed effect terms refer to the groups of explanatory variables expressing the research hypotheses. Functions $f_i()$ express that different formats of the model terms were explored: for instance, *Climate* was available as both a categorical variable (climate zone or climate group) and with the analytical variables rain, temperature, potential evapotranspiration and the aridity index. Moreover, to allow for nonlinear relationships, the numerical variables were expressed in the log-scale or were categorized in two (C2) or three classes (C3). The interaction terms with *Distance* and the other explanatory variables (as expressed with the interaction symbol *) allowed to modify the slope of the *Distance* function.

The random effect term assigned to each study site modeled the correlation structure within the study sites because of the repeated measures. As expressed by Study:Site, different sites within the same study received a different random effect. Site indicates each experimental site where a crop was investigated for each year of study. Therefore, for each Study there were as many Sites as the number of crop × year × site. It was not possible to fit a hierarchical effect (Study/Site) as the dataset was highly unbalanced. Some studies contained many sites with few observations, while others contained few sites or even one site.

2.5. The model building strategy

Because of the many variables to explore and in order to guarantee interpretable models, a forward regression strategy was used to build models, and variables were step by step included representing the research hypotheses as summarized in Table 2. At each step, alternative variables were screened, and the best model was selected based on regression diagnostics and visualized for its ecological meaning before continuing.

In the first step, the yield expressed as RR was modeled as a function of the distance from the tree row; it was a major feature of the data as it is not meaningful to study the impact of other variables without taking into account this major factor. To allow comparisons among different studies and trials, the distance was expressed in relative terms to the height of the tree row as ratio of the distance from the tree row (D) to the height of the trees (H) (D/H). Tree height was reported for the majority of the studies; when not available, it was estimated based on tree species and age. To linearize the distance trend, D/H was log-transformed (ln (D/H)) and the relation $RR \sim \ln(D/H)$ was tested as the base model for step 1 (RQ1).

This first step resulted in the base model expressing the fundamental relation of yield and distance (RQ1). Next, the specific impact of the crop species and its phenology was investigated (RQ2). The special point of interest was whether crop phenology (winter or summer) could explain an itself important part of the total variability without referring to a specific crop species. Both an additive and interaction relation with $\ln(D/H)$ were explored and the two competing phenology and crop models were compared both numerically and graphically. The result of the second step was called the core model as it was the point of departure for further refinements. In the next two steps, many explanatory variables were screened groupwise to improve the core models. In step 3 the impact of the tree characteristics (including tree age) and the tree row design (RQ3) were explored extending the core model, as well as in step 4 with the climate variables (RQ4). As the relationship is not necessarily linear, log-transformed and categorized variables were considered as detailed in SI.7. This resulted in several competing models investigated globally with both the information indices AIC and BIC and more in detail graphically. The IC gives an overall appreciation of the goodness of fit considering the model complexity, while the graphical approach allowed to appreciate whether model quality was uniform over the range of the explanatory variables.

The global screening relied on an information-theoretic perspective (Burnham and Anderson, 2014). Two complementary information criteria (IC) were used: Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). Both criteria make a trade-off between goodness of fit as expressed by the deviance of the model (lower values are better) and model complexity as expressed by the number of parameters (lower number is better). However, for BIC, the penalty for model complexity is higher, favoring more simple models. Considering both criteria simultaneously provided insights on whether there was no overfitting.

To oversee many competing models, a graphical tool was developed to visualize the trade-off between AIC and BIC. In this graph, by group of variables, the competing models were ordered as function of BIC, to facilitate the choice of the optimal model(s) and to contrast the evolution of BIC with AIC. Model screening followed some inclusion criteria:

- In case of a severe conflict between AIC and BIC outputs, BIC was considered as a warning for model complexity and overfitting, and the model was rejected;
- With similar AIC and BIC outputs, the choice of the optimal model considered (i) the regression diagnostics, (ii) the level of data coverage, and (iii) ecological meaning of the candidate models.

Data coverage of a model is related to data balance: for each range or combination of variables, the model should contain sufficient data to verify the model. This is a criterion often overlooked and is linked with the concept of model extrapolation. Regression models are very good in interpolation, but function bad when extended beyond the observation range.

Statistical analyses were performed in R version 3.4.4 (The R Foundation for Statistical Computing Platform, 2024) and RStudio version 2023.12.1 (Posit Software, PBC, 2009–2024). The model building with mixed-effects regression models was carried out within the lme4 environment, i.e., with the 'lmer' function of the R package lme4 (Bates et al., 2015) in combination with the ggeffects package (Lüdtke, 2018) to visualize the models.

3. Results

3.1. Overall effect, study heterogeneity and publication bias

Response ratio ranged from -2.77 (94 % lower yield compared to the reference) for soybean at +2 m on the Northern side from an E-W oriented row of 9-year old *Eucalyptus* trees in Brazil (study ID#13) up to +0.57 (yield 77 % higher than the reference) for maize at +10 m from a

N-S oriented row of 6-year old poplar trees in Italy (study ID#17), both cases falling in the warm temperature with a hot summer climate (WT).

The meta-analysis of the entire dataset revealed a significant negative effect of tree row on crop grain yield, with an estimate of the summary effect size equal to -0.32 (relative yield loss by 30 %) [95 % confidence interval from -0.39 to -0.26] ($p \leq 0.001$). Heterogeneity among studies also showed to be significant, indicating high diversity in environmental and weather conditions, and particularities of the site/study, with an estimated amount of total heterogeneity τ^2 equal to 0.21 [95 % confidence interval = 0.20, 0.33] ($p \leq 0.001$), as detailed in SI.9.

The model building process, from the null to the full model, showed that the successive inclusion of relevant moderators reduced funnel plots asymmetry (SI.10). The base model with crop distance revealed to be slightly unbalanced. However, fitting the best full models with relevant explanatory variables showed no evidence for publication bias based on both visual estimation of funnel plots and Egger's test.

3.2. The model building process

Fig. 2 and SI.11 show how the model performance changes by inclusion of predictors reflecting the research hypotheses (Table 2) in a forward regression. The top panel represents the starting point, while the panels below build further on the optimal model in the top model. Within each panel, the models are ranked by BIC, and it is checked whether AIC follows the same trend to control for overfitting. If a major discrepancy occurs, then the model is ruled out, as seen in case for instance for the model with tree species. Although AIC favored this model overall, it has very high BIC value indicating overfitting. It is the worst model within the panel investigating the impact of tree row variables. As there are many different tree species, the number of parameters in the model is ultimately very high. This high complexity results in a good fit, but the BIC criterion indicates overfitting due to the high number of parameters involved.

As regards crop type variables, i.e., crop species and phenology, they were confirmed to be a significant explanatory variable of the response ratio, as reflected by the significant drop in both AIC and BIC as compared to the base model (SI.11). With crop type variables included in the model, the choice of the linear relation ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H)$ ' over a polynomial one was also verified. Although AIC favored the polynomial fit, the linear relation was kept, due to (i) higher BIC value for the polynomial, warning for model complexity, and (ii) limited range of $\ln(D/H)$ covered by the observations, specifically the lack of data $> \ln(D/H) = \sim 0$.

Crop species and phenology allowed for a very similar improvement of the base model, with AIC favoring the first, and BIC the latter, although slightly (SI.11). As the gain in AIC and BIC achieved with these two moderators was the largest among all the competing variables, ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * \text{crop_species}$ ' (crop_DH) and ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * \text{crop phenology}$ ' (pheno_DH) were both defined as the core models of the dataset and both tracks were investigated further. The inclusion of additional relevant moderators in the subsequent model building was pursued with both core models. Fig. 2 and SI.11 show the AIC and BIC results of model building with pheno_DH, since it scored consistently better on the BIC criterion, as in line with the inclusion criteria for model screening. In the supplementary material, SI.12 shows the results of the alternative track with crop_DH as a starting point.

In the model building with pheno_DH, regardless of the variable included, the number of alternative models yielding better than the pheno_DH model was generally limited, highlighting the strength of the pattern fit by this model to the dataset (Fig. 2). Both AIC and BIC indicated that a relevant improvement of the core model could be achieved by including tree age. Across tree age-models, the trajectories of AIC and BIC outputs showed that the relation with age is not linear (as represented by age_orig: original tree age values), while the log2-scale of the original variable gives a better relationship, but does not succeed in modelling the nonlinearity properly, as the two categorizations of age

Fig. 2. Screening of competitor models starting from the base model with distance (dist_DH) and the core model with crop phenology. The top panel compares the base model with distance only and the two core models extending the base model with phenology or crop. The black squares indicate AIC/BIC for the base model dist_DH. These values are adjusted downwards to not distort the readability of the graph. The other panels below start from the core model chosen and include crop, tree age, tree row and climate characteristics to test the research hypotheses (see Table 2) and to find out the optimal model format. If none of the models in a certain group scores better than the core model, the group is considered as not relevant. The models (y-axis) are ordered by BIC to reveal discrepancies with AIC easily. Additional information about the characteristics and performances of these competitor models are available in SI.11.

(three class ‘age_C3’ and two class ‘age_C2’ variables) scored better. More generally, although by definition AIC-values are lower than BIC-values, the ranking of tree age-models remained very similar as seen from both perspectives. In particular, the class variable with two binary categories of age was favored more by BIC than by AIC due to its simplicity, showing the best performance as compared to all the other age variable formats. Conversely, the addition of none of the other tree row characteristics performed better than the pheno_DH model, although similar BIC outputs to the core models were achieved with the distance between trees along the row as three class variable (dinrow_C3) (Fig. 2, SI.11).

The addition of age_C2 to the pheno_DH model performed better than any other alternative models, as reflected by both the AIC and BIC indexes, resulting in the best model across all those investigated (Fig. 2). Nevertheless, climatic variables improved model quality (lower BIC values) as compared to the core model, particularly when including

cumulative rainfall from sowing-to-harvesting (rainG) and year evapotranspiration (petY), both in the original and log2-scales, while the aridity index (aridG) scored similarly to the core model. In contrast, the two categorical variables related to the different climatic area —the temperate climate subgroup (Köppen–Geiger) (clim_zone_KG) and an alternative classification based on the contrast between low/high for air temperature and rainfall (clim_zone_TR4) (Table 1, SI.7)— did not improve the core model. However, the latter scored much better than the former in terms of both AIC and BIC and gave similar output to the core model.

When comparing the outputs of model building with pheno_DH (Fig. 2) and crop_DH (SI.12) as core models, the results appeared remarkably similar, although some variations can be observed. A first general feature is that with crop_DH as the core, the contrast between AIC and BIC was much larger than in Fig. 2, as expected due to the larger number of parameters to be estimated in the crop model. Moreover, the

BIC scores for the crop model were in most cases worse than with the phenology core model. Yet, the BIC scores of the tree age-models attained similar values, confirming the impact of tree age. In contrast, the tree row parameters became less important, confirming the analysis in Fig. 2. Also, including the continuous climate variables to the crop model did not imply an improvement from the BIC perspective, however, from the AIC perspective there seemed to be a large gain (SI.12), supporting the evidence of a relevant impact of climate. However, the dataset is not sufficiently large to rule out which climate format performed best, as depending on the perspective other models were classified as the best.

3.3. Model visualization: distance from the tree row (RQ1) and crop type (RQ2)

According with the initial hypotheses (H2), a contrasting yield response between winter and summer crops was confirmed, with the first group being less negatively affected by tree presence than summer crops, as revealed in Fig. 3. Within winter crops, a different slope of $RR \sim \ln(D/H)$ regression lines was further revealed. In particular, barley was the least impaired by tree row proximity across all the investigated crops, revealing a nearly null effect of trees on grain yield, as reflected by the flat regression line. When examining at different D/H intervals, a significant barley RR decrease was observed only when D/H was lower than 0.25 ($RR = -0.16$, $[-0.28, -0.01]$), with 15 % lower yield vs. C (SI.14). In wheat, the slope of the regression line indicated a greater yield decrease as the tree row approaches, with a significant negative effect until a D/H value between 0.5 and 1 (SI.13), i.e., ~ -33 % of grain yield from the tree row to D/H = 0.5 and -16 % at the inter-row width interval between D/H = 0.5 and D/H = 1 (SI.14). Across the two summer crops, regression lines of the core model ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * \text{crop species}$ ' were parallel, reflecting a similar pattern of yield decrease for maize and soybean when getting closer to the tree line. However, the largest yield loss, compared to full sun, was observed in soybean. This is shown by the lower intercept of the regression line, and significant yield reductions along the entire investigated inter-row, always exceeding 40 % yield loss vs. C and reaching -75 % at the closest D/H interval (D/H

< 0.25 ; SI.13 and SI.14). In maize, instead, significant yield losses compared to full sun were limited to the inter-row width interval between D/H = 0 and D/H = 0.5 (SI.13), with an average yield loss of -64 % and -37 % vs. C, respectively at D/H < 0.25 and at 0.25–0.5 inter-row width intervals. In general, $\ln(D/H) = 0$, i.e., when the distance from the tree row is equal to tree height, emerged as a relevant threshold. In fact, in the four crop species this is the distance at which RR approaches 0, meaning that grain yield is recovered and reaches a similar value as in the full sun control (Fig. 3).

3.4. Model visualization: tree and design characteristics (RQ3)

Among tree and design characteristics, only tree age contributed to a relevant improvement of the core models, with the two-class variable 'age_C2' showing the greatest drop in both AIC and BIC (Fig. 2, SI.11).

The graphical visualization of the age_C2 model highlights that the negative impact of the tree row on grain yield increases with tree age, with the ranking from young (≤ 8 years old: lower slope) to old trees (> 8 years old: higher slope) maintained across all crop species (Fig. 4). In winter crops, different patterns were revealed depending on tree age: in wheat, only the older trees caused a decreasing RR with tree proximity, while young trees had no effect; in barley, in contrast, old trees had a nearly null effect, whereas young trees had beneficial ($RR > 1$) effects, increasing productivity as they approached the tree row. In summer crops, the grain yield was always negatively affected, regardless of the tree age, and was much more severely impacted than in winter crops with old trees.

3.5. Model visualization: climatic characteristics (RQ4)

Given the interest in the impact of all quantitative climatic variables, all models with climate moderators (original scale) as growing season means (G format) were plotted for the crop_DH core model. As expected, pet and temp revealed patterns very similar to one another within the same crop species, and were opposite to rain and arid (Fig. 5). When considering pet and temp, the trend of RR decreases when getting close to the tree row was the lowest with high values of both parameters, and

Fig. 3. Graphical visualization of the core model of the dataset: grain yield variation (RR yield) in response to the distance to the tree row, expressed as the \ln of the ratio of the distance from the tree row (D) to the height of the trees (H) ($\ln(D/H)$), according to crop phenology and species. Black lines represent the slope estimate of the core model ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * \text{crop phenology}$ '; colored lines represent the slope estimate of the core model ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * \text{crop species}$ ', respectively for barley (red), winter wheat (green), maize (blue) and soybean (purple). Points represent individual observations, and grey bands represent the confidence bands (95 % confidence intervals). A positive response ratio ($RR > 0$) means that the presence of the tree row has a positive effect on the crop yield, i.e., higher yield vs. C, while a negative response ratio ($RR < 0$) means a negative effect of trees on crop yield, and effect sizes close to zero ($RR \approx 0$) indicate little or no effect. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Graphical visualization of the full model including tree age: grain yield variation (RR yield) in response to $\ln(D/H)$, according to tree age, expressed as categorical variable, and crop species. Lines represent the slope estimate of the full model ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * (\text{crop species} + \text{tree age}_C)$ ', respectively for trees ≤ 8 years old (red) and > 8 years old (blue). Points represent individual observations, and red or blue bands represent the confidence bands of the regression lines (95 % confidence intervals). A positive response ratio ($RR > 0$) means that the presence of the tree row has a positive effect on the crop yield, i.e., higher yield vs. C, while a negative response ratio ($RR < 0$) means a negative effect of trees on crop yield, and effect sizes close to zero ($RR \approx 0$) indicate little or no effect. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Graphical visualization of four of the full models including climatic characteristics: grain yield variation (RR yield) in response to $\ln(D/H)$, according to four climate variables and crop species. The four models included potential evapotranspiration (pet), rainfall (rain) and air temperature (air) as a categorical variable, considering the growing-to-harvesting (G) mean. Lines represent the slope estimate of the full model ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H) * (\text{crop species} + \text{climate})$ ', respectively for low (red), middle (green) and high (blue) categories (defined in SI.7 and SI.8) of the climatic variables considered. A positive response ratio ($RR > 0$) means that the presence of the tree row has a positive effect on the crop yield, i.e., higher yield vs. C, while a negative response ratio ($RR < 0$) means a negative effect of trees on crop yield, and effect sizes close to zero ($RR \approx 0$) indicate little or no effect. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the highest with low pet and temp (SI.8). The most relevant RR recovery, or even improvement, with tree vicinity were therefore associated to years and location with high pet and temp. Among crop species, only barley revealed beneficial effects by tree vicinity ($RR > 0$) within both medium and high temp and pet. Summer crops, instead, besides the different slope of the regression lines, always reduced grain yield to values largely below $RR = 0$ within all pet and temp categories. When considering rain and arid, regression lines across categories differed less as compared to pet and temp, especially for winter crops. However, the trend of RR recovery when approaching the tree row was the highest with low rain and arid, and the lowest with high rain and arid (SI.8). Consequently, crops took the greatest advantage from tree proximity during years and/or location characterized by lower cumulative rainfall and aridity index. Across crop species, barley was associated with a null ($RR = 0$) or slightly beneficial ($RR > 0$) effect of trees under middle and low rainfall, respectively. In all the other crops, a detrimental effect of trees ($RR < 0$) with tree proximity was observed within all rain and arid categories, although slopes of the regression lines differed (Fig. 5). In particular, soybean crop differed from all the above crops, as it showed parallel regression lines across all the climatic parameters and the three categories (low vs. middle vs. high), although the ranking from low to high was always associated to an increasing negative impact on grain yield.

4. Discussion

This meta-analysis provided a comprehensive summary of crop yield responses in alley-cropping systems across the entire temperate climatic zone, focusing on arable grain crops. Modelling allowed to identify the following key findings: (i) the crop distance from trees is the major driver of the grain yield response, with the highest yield reductions obtained close to the tree line and a gradual restoration when the ratio of the distance from trees to height (D/H) increases, (ii) crop phenology and species are both significant explanatory variables, with a lower impact of tree vicinity on the yield in winter crops, particularly barley, vs. summer crops; (iii) tree age is the only relevant explanatory variable across tree and design characteristics, with a more negative impact on crop yield as the tree age increases, suggesting that age is a good proxy for tree size and its competitive effects on the neighboring crops; and (iv) across additional potential moderators regarding climate, the cumulative rainfall available to the crop and the potential evapotranspiration, and their ratio as aridity index, are the most informative ones, with a less detrimental or even positive impact of the tree row on crop yield within years and/or locations with low rainfall and aridity indices, and high evapotranspiration.

4.1. The crop distance to the tree-row relative to the tree height

The average crop yield reduction within agroforestry systems, here estimated as -30% vs. the full sun control, is in line with previous meta-analyses within the European context (between -20 and -50% ; Ivezic et al., 2021; Scordia et al., 2023) and the temperate area of China (-39% ; Visscher et al., 2023). However, this meta-analysis innovatively indicates that behind this average yield reduction, there is a wide variability driven by the distance from the tree row, the crop type, the tree age and the specific climatic conditions. The distance from trees-to-the tree height ratio (D/H) was here revealed as the main explanatory variable of the yield response. This outcome differed from previous meta-analyses on alley-cropping systems where distance was not significant due to the small variation in width of the alleys (Ivezic et al., 2021) or because not investigated (Scordia et al., 2023). The wide range of inter-rows considered in this study, i.e., from 5 m (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2018) to more than 50 m (Pardon et al., 2018), and the specific choice of data collection, allowed to appreciate the significant

variability of crop yield across the alley and how the relation $RR \sim \ln(D/H)$ changes according to the other variables. A significant effect of crop distance was previously observed by Van Vooren et al. (2017) only, over 60 studies from temperate climates. However, while Van Vooren et al. (2017) summarized the effect of hedgerows, and suggested a negative effect on crop yield between $D/H = 0.0$ and $D/H = 2.1$, the present study included only alley-cropping systems with regularly pruned and branchless trees, which revealed a negative impact on crop yield until a D/H ratio of about 1. Therefore, innovative alley-cropping systems with regularly pruned trees is suggested as a promising choice in order to optimize tree-crop interactions and ensure high crop productivity, as it allows for roughly halving the field width where crop yield is negatively impacted by the tree line compared to hedgerows. Additionally, some recommendations about the optimization of the inter-row distance can be made. In agreement with the argument by Van Lerberghe et al. (2017), indeed, for a sustainable long-term system the distance between tree rows should be at least twice the height of mature trees. This set-up ensures a considerable width at the centre of the inter-row where competitive interaction with trees is limited and the crop yield is comparable or even higher than that of a full sun condition. Depending on the tree species, rows spacing between 25 and 50 m are therefore suggested to optimize tree-crop productivity. On the other hand, it was recently highlighted that the structural diversity, layering, and density parameters characterizing an “hedge-like” structure are strongly positively correlated with provision of ecosystem services, including microclimate regulation, improved animal species diversity, soil protection and pest control, while hedgerow length, width and age showed less relevant relationships (Weninger et al., 2021; Kratschmer et al., 2024). As a consequence, the relevant gain in crop production achievable with tree rows made by one or two layers of branchless trees as compared to hedgerows, is expected to occur at the expenses of ecosystem services. However, besides the structure and density of the tree row, it was reported that the choice of low and narrow tree row bands goes at the advantage of crop production but not at the expenses of ecosystem services delivery, versus high and large tree rows (Van Vooren et al., 2017; Ivezic et al., 2022). In any case, if a lower treeline is achievable through a proper choice of the tree species and cultivar/variety, i.e., by favoring those with low-height characteristics, and/or through adapted pruning techniques, the reduction of the tree row width might have some logistic/practical implications that are more complex to be addressed. Indeed, all tree-related management activities that require the transit of machinery along the tree line have a negative impact on the potential crop production, either because the tree row band is widened, thereby reducing the crop width, or because the transit of machinery damages the crop growth and yield in case of a tree band width that is limited to the tree line (1 to 2 m). The choice of the treeline width is certainly a major aspect for optimizing alley-cropping design. In the case of fruit tree species, the tree row band is suggested to be wide enough to allow for all the tree-related activities, as they commonly require more frequent interventions vs. timber trees in order to ensure protection, and especially in the case of nut species, for which a soil covered with grass and mowed is fundamental for an efficient fruit harvesting. In the case of timber trees, instead, the choice of the tree band width is less evident and case-specific: allowing the crop cultivation band till very close to the tree line might be a good option when (i) the transit of machinery for tree management is rare and/or not concurrent with the crop growing cycle, and (ii) the crop species and/or management are suitable for limiting the negative impact of machineries transit. Specifically, lower crop impairments can be expected in the case of row crops like soybean and maize, as the large crop inter-row allows machineries transit until a certain stage of crop growth and soil coverage, and also in the case of forage crops, for which this might be less detrimental vs. grain crops.

4.2. Yield response across different crop phenology and species

Besides tree proximity, the impact of tree rows on the crop yield is strongly influenced by the crop type. The gain in model quality achieved by incorporating both crop phenology and species into the base model ' $RR \sim \ln(D/H)$ ' was the largest across all the investigated moderators, confirming that they are essential elements to assess the grain yield response in alley-cropping systems. Notably, the core model with crop phenology captures the core dynamics, confirming the critical distinction between winter and summer crops; winter crops are less affected by trees as compared to the latter (Piotto et al., 2024; Pardon et al., 2018). Indeed, barley and winter wheat, both C3 plants with minimal overlap in growing seasons with deciduous tree species, exhibited the least yield losses in the area neighboring tree rows, when compared to light-demanding summer crops such as maize and soybean (Reynolds et al., 2007; Gill et al., 2009; Jose et al., 2004; Pardon et al., 2018).

In addition to the contrast between winter and summer crops, an effect of crop species was also revealed. The relevance of crop species was associated mainly to the different responses among winter species, while summer crops revealed very similar patterns of $RR \sim \ln(D/H)$ regression lines. Barley was indeed the least affected by proximity to the tree rows, by observing yield reduction only between $D/H = 0$ and $D/H = 0.25$ of very old trees in areas with medium and high rainfall patterns. It exhibited better adaptability to alley-cropping even compared to winter wheat, in view of its earlier phenological development and lower light saturation point, these being key traits for both shade avoidance (lower overlap in growing season) and tolerance (lowers light requirements) (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2018). The two winter cereals were found to also vary in terms of acclimatization strategies to low-irradiance environments, with barley primarily relying on physiological acclimatization, while wheat revealed a major morphological adjustment (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2018).

In contrast to winter crops, variations between the available species within summer crops were very low, with the yield of both maize and soybean being similarly and significantly reduced at all distances up to $D/H = 1$ and regardless any tree, design and climate characteristic choices. Soybean proved to be slightly more affected by the tree row than maize, particularly under the specificities of alley-cropping systems within the temperate climate of Brazil, with E-W oriented tree lines and very narrow inter-rows (6 to 12 m) (Cristo et al., 2020; Sgarbossa et al., 2018, 2020). A recent meta-analysis on the susceptibility of different temperate crops to increasing shading levels (Laub et al., 2022) highlighted the low tolerance of grain legumes to shade, with yield losses more than proportional to the reduction in solar radiation even at very low shade levels. In accordance, relevant yield impairments of soybean, as revealed by this meta-analysis, but also faba bean and winter field pea, as reported by Scordia et al. (2023), are to be expected in alley-cropping models across the whole temperate climatic zone. Previous studies associated these reductions of soybean grain yield to typical shade avoidance responses like internode lengthening and considerable stem elongation (Liu et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2017), that often led to plant lodging (Liu et al., 2016). Maize, as a C4 plant with high solar radiation requirements, is highly sensitive to light restrictions (Gao et al., 2020), showing marked yield losses close to tree rows across the whole temperate area. Shaded maize leaves showed reduced photosynthetic efficiency and resource competition directly with cob development in terms of assimilate allocation, resulting in reduced seed yield and harvest index, or even sterility (Collison et al., 2020).

4.3. Tree and design characteristics

Besides tree proximity and crop type, only tree age allowed to improve model quality across all the tree and design characteristics available. As reported in previous empirical studies and meta-analyses (Ivezić et al., 2021), this meta-analysis confirmed the increasing competitive effects of aging trees. A tree age around eight years emerged

to be a meaningful threshold between young trees causing a limited reduction or even an improvement of grain yield, and older trees having a greater detrimental impact, regardless of the crop and tree species choices. This corroborates the arguments of previous authors, setting the turning point between 7 (Pardon et al., 2018; Carrier et al., 2019) or 10 (Graves et al., 2010; Gold and Garrett, 2009) years age. Although tree age as a categorical variable yielded the highest model quality across all the tested models with 3 variables, we suggest considering it with caution. This is because the split into two age categories was arbitrary and the outcome might be influenced by the specific configuration of this dataset. Nevertheless, the improved quality of all the models including tree age, with all the tested age formats, suggests that tree age can be considered a good proxy for tree size and competitive resource demands, despite the substantial difference between tree species in their rate of growth. As for the other potential moderators regarding design choices, none of them provided additional useful information to the core model, again confirming the strength of this key feature in the dataset.

4.4. Yield variability across different climatic conditions

Climate variables were revealed to be highly relevant to the patterns of grain yield variability across the tree line inter-row, as compared to full sun monocultures. Interestingly, the differences across temperate climatic zones, as defined by the Koppen classifications, were not sufficient to properly describe crop yield responses, while the high diversity of quantitative climatic variables specific for each study site was essential. Both cumulative rainfall (rain) and mean evapotranspiration (pet) have shown to be key drivers of the grain productivity in the vicinity of a tree row, as suggested by the relevant improvements of the core model. Pet achieved the best model quality, suggesting it to be a good surrogate for climatic conditions. Indeed, it can be considered a summary climate variable, in view of the many variables considered in its calculations, i.e., from the Penman – Monteith formula, which takes into account net radiation at crop surface, the soil heat flux, the average air temperature at 2 m height, the windspeed measured at 2 and 10 m height, the vapor pressure deficit for measurement at 2 m height, and the slope of the vapor pressure curve, together with a constant and a coefficient for the reference crop (Harris et al., 2020). Therefore, given the low performance of mean air temperature (temp) revealed in the model screening, pet can be used as a good proxy for air temperature as well. Here, grain crops take better advantage of tree proximity within years and/or sites characterized by low rainfall and aridity index, and/or high potential evapotranspiration and air temperature. Contrastingly, the grain yield is more severely impaired by approaching the tree row within years and/or sites with high rainfall and aridity index, and/or low pet and temp. This confirms the hypothesis that the protection role of trees on crops is more evident under drought and heat stress, and within high evapotranspiration conditions, where positive interactions exceed competitiveness. This was true for all the studied crop species, although with different patterns of yield variability across the inter-row. In settings of low water availability, and medium and high temp and pet, the yield of barley always benefited from tree presence, confirming the high drought tolerance of this winter cereal (Scordia et al., 2023), while wheat productivity took advantage only in years and/or sites with high temp and pet. Studies fitting in these challenging climates are mostly located in the Mediterranean region, supporting the definition of a climate change hotspot over this climatic zone (Tuel and Eltahir, 2020). However, in this area winter cereals can benefit the most from alley-cropping models, following the improvement of water relations, but also the mitigation of extreme temperatures and wind speed, as compared to conventional monoculture. Previous studies reported that irradiance usually exceeds plant requirements in the Mediterranean area, making competition for solar radiation negligible, while water represents the main limiting resource (Ivezić et al., 2021; Eichhorn et al., 2006). However, our study innovatively indicates that the major benefits of alley-cropping are in water limited and high pet conditions,

suggesting agroforestry as a reliable solution to improve crop resilience to climate change right in the Mediterranean area. In very favorable climatic conditions for winter cereal grain production, temperatures fitting crop requirements and adequate rainfall during spring, trees are expected to be more detrimental to grain yield, as observed in a previous study (Arenas-Corraliza et al., 2018). For summer crops, the protection role of trees within low rainfall and/or high pet and temp conditions is still visible, but it is not sufficient to compensate irradiance reduction compared to full sun conditions. Within the temperate region of the world, here it was demonstrated that tree-crop competition for resources always exceeded positive interactions in soybean and maize, and yield losses are to be expected in the proximity of tree rows, regardless of the tree and design characteristics. A different response has already been described within the tropical and subtropical regions in a recent meta-analysis by Baier et al. (2023), who related the most relevant benefits from agroforestry to maize yield in strongly water limited environments.

4.5. The role of microclimate variations within the inter-row

The mechanisms behind the protective role of trees in extreme or stressful climates are complex, involving both above- and below-ground interactions with the understory crop. Tree canopies are known to reduce the desiccant effect of wind, even before leafing (Gea-Izquierdo et al., 2009), and to decrease the water loss through evapotranspiration (Siriri et al., 2013), while improving soil water infiltration. Air temperature buffering is another important environmental benefit associated with agroforestry practices, with high potential to reduce temperature extremes, as already reported within both the tropical (Sida et al., 2018; Kuyah et al., 2019) and the temperate climates. In the temperate climates of Europe, mean air temperature reductions from -1.2 to -3.4 °C were measured during the growing cycle of winter cereals cultivated in the inter-row of alley-cropping systems (Panozzo et al., 2022; Inurreta-Aguirre et al., 2018; Kanzler et al., 2019). The greatest benefits occur later in the season, particularly during the grain filling stage of wheat, which is the highly sensitive to high temperatures and drought-factors decisive for productivity and quality.

Furthermore, a key question in tree-crop interactions is whether trees can move water from deeper soil horizons to reduce competition with annual crops in the topsoil (Sida et al., 2018). Some authors have also considered the process of hydraulic lift as a possible mechanism for increasing soil moisture in shallow soil layers (Luo et al., 2022; Schoeneberger et al., 2012). Although the hydraulic lift has been reported in species such as *Quercus* sp., *Pinus* sp. and *Ziziphus* sp., with a high contribution in agroforestry farming systems (Filella and Peñuelas, 2003; Eliades et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2014), scientific evidence is not yet available for the most common tree species in temperate alley-cropping systems. At belowground level, previous studies have also highlighted the drought-alleviating capacities of mycorrhizal fungi associated to tree roots (Baier et al., 2023). Trees can act as reservoir for an abundant mycelial network accessible to crops (Isaac and Borden, 2019), and they also enhance the richness of mycorrhizal fungal communities compared to monocultures (Chiffot et al., 2009), improving crops' resistance to drought (Boomsma and Vyn, 2008). These benefits become particularly evident under drought stress but are also relevant when water is not a limiting factor (Augé, 2001; Lawson et al., 2019).

4.6. Data strengths and limitations, and the model building process

The conclusions of this study must be considered in view of some specific characteristics of the dataset. A rather strictly standardized process for study collection based on the PRISMA method was here adopted. The systematic literature search and the inclusion criteria might not have gathered all relevant publications addressing the research question of the meta-analysis. Indeed, the search terms might have missed information in grey literature, especially in non-English publications, and in local non-scientific reports. Furthermore, the

inclusion criteria, especially regarding the necessity to have true controls present nearby the silvoarable plot, forced us to disregard several publications. However, the strict observance of the PRISMA method and the inclusion criteria allowed not to incur in flawed approaches or low-quality data.

Lastly, the number of studies retained was limited, $n = 18$, despite the relatively high number of observations ($n = 217$), with two studies from Belgium proving 54 % of the observations ($n = 118$). The consistency of the Belgian data with other studies was visually checked and did not show any major discrepancies. With respect to the geographic location, more than half of the studies (55.6 %) came from Europe ($n = 10$); while regarding climatic conditions, five studies were from MC (n of observations = 22 = 10 %), 4 from OC ($n = 130 = 59$ %), and nine from the WT ($n = 65 = 30$ %).

A strength of the dataset was that crop distance to the tree row was available in all the studies, and it was used as a key element of model building to correct for distance effects. However, different methodologies for calculating the crop distance to the tree row across the different studies, or measurement error, might have an impact on the results. In particular, because of the log-scale, a mistake in the measurement of distance close to the tree row has higher impact vs. farther positions. Moreover, the distance range covered was heterogeneous across studies. In general, crop yield data covered the range from positions very close to the tree line up to $D/H = 1$, not more, which impeded extending the model beyond $D > H$, which would be very informative as suggested by previous studies (Van Vooren et al., 2017).

Because of the many variables and the rather small dataset, there was a risk of overfitting. Also, multicollinearity was a challenge as the crop distribution follows closely the climate variables. Hence, it is hard to disentangle climate effects from crop species effects. For all these reasons a step-up forward regression procedure was followed. At each step, it was evaluated whether the model was ecologically sound, and the data coverage (balance) was sufficient. This transparent approach helped to discriminate among variables of potential interest and those without any consistent signal. By considering model complexity, the gains in model performance were modest when compared to the core models. Yet, the IC criteria are just an overall appreciation of the model quality, without judging the finer details of the model fit. Residual analysis and model visualization allowed for the detection of systematic defects in the model and helped to select the variables that improve the model. For example, although the BIC criterion favored the model with phenology only, there was evidence for a systematic crop species effect as indicated by the AIC. In this way, the selection process was transparent and avoided the main pitfalls of blind model fitting. It was also a guarantee that the models were close to the data, ecologically sound and interpretable.

4.7. Perspectives on crop rotation and variety choice

The limited number of studies that met the inclusion criteria of this meta-analysis provides a partial picture of field crops' response to alley-cropping systems. The analysis is restricted to four crops, and highlights the urgent need to quantify the yield response of other inter-crops potentially adapted to agroforestry. However, these results are already highly informative for planning a suitable crop rotation in alley-cropping models, as function of tree age and specific climatic conditions.

During the first part of the tree cycle, when the competitive effect of trees is still moderate, light-and-water demanding crops should be favored, such as maize and soybean as summer crops and wheat as winter crop. During the second part of the tree's life, when shading and water competition become more relevant, the cultivation of adapted species is fundamental, especially under relevant abiotic stresses. This meta-analysis confirms barley as a suitable winter crop for mature alley-cropping design, particularly in the sites where challenging environmental conditions are frequent, while primary quantitative information on suitable summer crops is still needed to optimize an efficient crop rotation.

Spatial differentiation across the inter-row can also be suggested, with bands of crops/varieties more tolerant to tree proximity planted close to the tree row, and bands of less tolerant ones in the center of the alley. In this strip cropping design, the number of bands, and therefore the number of crops/varieties across the alley, could be determined by some practical and technical considerations, like the width of the alley and the size of machinery, but also by the level of complexity which is advantageous, based on the type of management and the objectives of the farmer.

The implementation of high-productive alley-cropping systems can be achieved through a deeper understanding of multiple tree-crop interactions that affect growth and yield of herbaceous plants, with particular attention to variety choice. To date, genetic variability (intra-specific level) within field crops has been poorly investigated for these purposes, and mainly in pot trials with artificial shading. Arenas-Corraliza et al. (2021) assessed the effect of artificial shade on multiple Mediterranean wheat and barley varieties of different precocity categories, finding significant differences between cultivars in terms of grain yield increase, leaf mass area decreases and total chlorophyll content increase under shade conditions. Additionally, Panozzo et al. (2020) observed a clear difference in shade response between old and modern Mediterranean durum wheat varieties, namely in grain yield and grain quality. However, studies examining field crops responses at variety level are quite rare, not allowing to carry out any comprehensive analysis and to make any consistent conclusion. In this meta-analysis, the crop variety was even not mentioned for half of the observations included in the dataset and very heterogeneous when available, hampering any proper analysis. However, the large variability in the yield response documented by the few studies that carried out variety comparisons suggests that there is reasonable scope in screening field crops varieties for agroforestry.

5. Conclusions

This meta-analysis enhances the understanding of the yield response of some widespread grain crops in temperate alley-cropping systems. Distance from the treeline, crop phenology and species, tree age, and specific climatic conditions were identified as key moderators of the crop grain productivity under agroforestry, relative to its full sun potential. Although this analysis is limited to four species, the choice of the crop was relevant, confirming over the whole temperate zone the major suitability of winter cereal vs. summer crops to alley-cropping models. Among summer crops, a decline in grain yield is commonly expected near tree rows, likely due to the large overlap with the tree foliage and irrespective of any tree species, design and climatic factors. In contrast, for winter crops the choice of the right crop for the right time and location can have a greater impact, with barley resulting in general to be more tolerant or even taking advantage of tree proximity compared to wheat.

The crop distance from trees was the major driver of the grain yield response, serving as a good proxy of the intensity of both facilitative and competitive interactions between trees and crops, depending on the specific climatic conditions. This study, for the first time, demonstrates that in temperate climates, the protective role of trees, reducing yield loss or even enhancing yield, is primarily observed during extreme climatic events, when positive interactions are stronger than competitive ones. Some innovative insights also emerge regarding design choices. Although the choice of N-S tree row orientation and large inter-rows are already commonly suggested to optimize the system design, some key differences on the effects of single layer and branchless tree row vs.

hedgerows are highlighted: while the latter maximize the provision of ecosystem services, the former allow for halving the alley width where crop yield is negatively affected by the tree line compared to a hedgerow, i.e., until a D/H ratio of about 1. Besides the structure of the tree row, the age was found to be the best performing moderator among all the tree, design and climate variables, highlighting that the choice of the crops in the rotation should be tailored to each phase of tree age, in order to maximize the yield potential of intercrops. When the trees approach about eight years of age seems a relevant threshold defining the beginning of a second phase of the system development where the intensity level of tree-crop competitive interactions requires the choice of crops and varieties with greater tolerance to tree competition.

This meta-analysis underscores the need for further empirical studies addressing the gaps identified here that prevent to draw a complete understanding of field crops response to alley-cropping. Key gaps concern primarily other intercrops which yield has been very little or not yet investigated under silvoarable systems, despite their economic value and potentially well suited to agroforestry, like sugar beet, sorghum and sunflower for summer crops, and oat, triticale and rye among winter cereals. Additional research should be carried out within climatic zones where limited data is currently available, such as (i) warm temperature with hot summer climates (WT), like the temperate areas of Eastern USA, China and South America, and the (ii) Mediterranean climates of the Balkan peninsula and northern Africa. Importantly, the high number of studies that were excluded from this meta-analysis suggest some key recommendations to make sure that future empirical studies are both designed and monitored in order to be correctly included and highly informative for future meta-analyses, i.e., (i) the implementation of a true crop control under full sun condition nearby the silvoarable plot, (ii) the use of replications to study the crop yield response, with an explicit indication of the sample size and relative estimates of uncertainty, and (iii) a detailed investigation of the tree phenological and morphological characteristics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anna Panozzo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Paul Quataert:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Tom De Swaef:** Writing – review & editing. **Paul Pardon:** Conceptualization. **Teofilo Vamerali:** Writing – review & editing. **Kris Verheyen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Bert Reubens:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2025.104578>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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